

ISB, ESB, ESMAC, GCMAS, and ASB Guidelines for Open Data Sharing in the Human Movement Sciences

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL S2: ADDITIONAL CONSIDERATIONS TO SUPPORT INFRASTRUCTURE
DEVELOPMENT FOR COMPLIANT OPEN DATA SHARING

S2.1 On data localisation vs. data sovereignty

As noted in the main text, Trusted Research Environments (TREs) are typically hosted on large-scale cloud infrastructure provided by companies such as Amazon Web Services, (AWS), Google Cloud Platform (GCP), and Microsoft Azure. These hyperscale providers offer highly scalable, secure, and compliant environments that can facilitate complex analytical workflows and international collaboration. While federated TREs hosted on such cloud platforms currently represent the most promising route for compliant data sharing, the specific choice of underlying cloud infrastructure warrants careful consideration, as not all implementations offer equivalent levels of legal data sovereignty.

Many jurisdictions (e.g. the European Union through the General Data Protection Regulation) have introduced requirements for data localisation, prompting cloud providers to develop region-specific offerings designed to ensure data storage and processing occur within defined geographic boundaries. However, physical data localisation alone does not fully address legal data sovereignty. The United States Clarifying Lawful Overseas Use of Data (CLOUD) Act [1], for example, enables U.S. authorities to request access to data held by U.S.-based providers regardless of where that data is physically stored [2], meaning assurances that data remain within a given jurisdiction may be technically accurate yet legally insufficient. While this tension has been most extensively documented in the context of European data protection frameworks, the underlying principle applies globally [3]; A critical distinction exists between data localisation and data sovereignty: while localisation addresses the physical storage of data, sovereignty additionally requires that data remain subject to the legal frameworks of the jurisdiction in which they are generated and governed. Researchers in any jurisdiction should therefore carefully evaluate not only where their data is physically stored, but under which legal frameworks their infrastructure provider operates.

S2.2 Balancing decentralised control with centralised coordination through a federated model

In a federated system, data remains decentralised by remaining at the site of origin to ensure that institutions retain control over access permissions, regulatory compliance, and legal accountability. At the same time, a centralised coordination layer allows researchers to search, identify, and request access to datasets across multiple institutions. In this context, decentralised

control and centralised coordination must act hand in hand: the former to ensure data remains subject to local institutional authority and legal frameworks, the latter to enable distributed nodes to function as part of a unified ecosystem. Realising this vision inherently requires compatibility across nodes, where all participating institutions adopt harmonised software components, data models, and interface standards that enable seamless integration. These will need to be coordinated, developed, and maintained by a central governing organisation, but critically, with essential active involvement from participating institutions to balance standardisation with the flexibility needed to accommodate diverse local needs. In this manner, a collaboratively governed federated ecosystem can provide the necessary structural foundation for compliant, scalable, and efficient data sharing in the human movement sciences.

S2.3 Guiding researchers through compliance with a step-by-step platform approach

The guidelines outlined in the main manuscript cover a broad range of ethical, legal, and technical considerations. For most researchers in the field, however, navigating regulatory compliance, data protection law, and secure data governance falls outside their core expertise, imposing a substantial burden and practical barrier to data sharing.

A centralised, user-oriented digital platform could address this gap by guiding researchers throughout the entire data sharing lifecycle. Such a platform, implemented as a web-based application, should provide structured workflows that translate regulatory and ethical requirements into actionable steps. This could include interactive forms, reusable templates, and context-specific guidance that assists researchers in generating compliant documentation without requiring extensive prior expertise (e.g. see Supplementary Material S1 and S3).

A critical first step in the workflow is preparing administrative and regulatory documentation. Here, the platform could provide pre-structured, legally validated, reusable templates for ethics applications, informed consent forms, and data management plans, where only study-specific elements need to be completed. Embedded guidance should clearly indicate which information is required and use standardised consent language that is aligned with ethical and legal regulations, while permitting future data sharing whenever possible. Not only would such practical guidance improve consistency across studies, but it would also reduce the administrative burden on individual research groups by removing the need for researchers to interpret regulatory requirements independently.

Once data has been collected, the platform should facilitate the structured submission of datasets and accompanying metadata. Harmonisation of metadata across contributing institutions is essential to enable meaningful aggregation and reuse of data. Established standards such as Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) [4] could enable integration with other clinical datasets and expand the scope of multimodal research, while lightweight alternatives such as RO-Crate [5] offer a more pragmatic entry point where ease of implementation is prioritised. Irrespective of the chosen standard, key requirements remain simplicity, interoperability, and both human- and machine-readability. By embedding metadata requirements directly into the

submission workflow, adherence to FAIR principles becomes an implicit part of the process rather than an additional task.

Once data has been submitted, the platform should serve as the central gateway through which researchers discover existing datasets and submit access requests. At this stage, a structured and context-specific de-identification and re-identification risk assessment should be initiated, as the appropriate level of de-identification will depend on the identity of the requester, the intended use, and the applicable jurisdiction. As outlined in established guidelines such as those of the Swiss Personalised Health Network (SPHN) [6], de-identification may require iterative case-by-case evaluation of residual re-identification risk rather than purely rules-based removal of identifiers. Access should only be granted once residual risk meets predefined acceptable thresholds, as agreed upon by a governing body of relevant stakeholders, with the direct input of the responsible ethics committees. Approved requests should then be fulfilled exclusively through a certified secure computational environment, such as the proposed TRE.

Finally, the platform should support mechanisms for persistent identification and citation of datasets. While Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) provide a widely adopted solution and should be included, they typically resolve to a direct download or access point and are therefore insufficient on their own to support controlled access workflows where users must first submit credentials, agree to terms of use, and obtain approval before accessing protected data. Platform-specific persistent identifiers could complement DOIs in this context, functioning as stable, citable references that route users through a compliant access request procedure rather than granting immediate access. This would support traceability and attribution while ensuring that controlled reuse remains enforced within the data sharing ecosystem. Together, the abovementioned platform components shift complexity from the individual researcher to the infrastructure, lowering barriers to participation and enabling compliant data sharing at scale.

Reference List

1. US Congress, H. R. 4943 — CLOUD Act. 2018 [cited April 28, 2026]; Available from: <https://www.congress.gov/115/bills/hr4943/BILLS-115hr4943ih.pdf>.
2. CMS Law, White Paper Demystifying the debate on the US CLOUD Act vs European/UK Data Sovereignty in the context of cloud services. 2026 [cited April 28, 2026]; Available from: <https://cms.law/en/aut/legal-updates/white-paper-demystifying-the-debate-on-the-us-cloud-act-vs-european-uk-data-sovereignty-in-the-context-of-cloud-services>.
3. Wire, What the CLOUD Act Really Means for EU Data Sovereignty. 2025 [cited April 28, 2026]; Available from: <https://wire.com/en/blog/cloud-act-eu-data-sovereignty>.
4. HL7 International, Fast Health Interoperability Resources (FHIR). 2026 [cited April 28, 2026]; Available from: <https://fhir.org/>.
5. Research Object Crate (RO-Crate). 2026 [cited April 28, 2026]; Available from: <https://www.researchobject.org/ro-crate/>.
6. Swiss Personalized Health Network (SPHN), SPHN Risk Assessment Template. 2026 [cited April 28, 2026]; Available from: <https://sphn.ch/network/data-coordination-center/de-identification/>.